

Original software publication

nabqr: Python package for correcting probabilistic forecasts

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ARTICLE INFO

Keywords:

Probabilistic forecasting
LSTM networks
Time adaptivity
Quantile regression
Wind power production

ABSTRACT

We introduce the open-source Python package NABQR: Neural Adaptive Basis for (time-adaptive) Quantile Regression that provides reliable probabilistic forecasts. NABQR corrects ensembles (scenarios) with LSTM networks and then applies time-adaptive quantile regression to the corrected ensembles to obtain improved and more reliable forecasts. With the developed package, we achieve substantial improvements for simulated wind power production data.

Code metadata

Current code version
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Software code languages, tools, and services used
Compilation requirements, operating environments & dependencies

If available Link to developer documentation/manual
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<https://github.com/ElsevierSoftwareX/SOFTX-D-25-00057>
<https://github.com/bast0320/nabqr/blob/main/src/NABQR/nabqr.py>
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git, pypi
Python, R
python ≥ 3.10 and the following packages: icecream, matplotlib, numpy, pandas, properscoring, rich, SciencePlots, scikit_learn, scipy, tensorflow, tensorflow_probability, torch, typer, myst_parser, tf_keras
R with the following packages installed: quantreg, readr
For example: <https://nabqr.readthedocs.io/en/latest/bassc@dtu.dk>

Abbreviations

Table 1.

1. Motivation and significance

Quantifying predictive uncertainty is a key challenge in many scientific fields that depend on model-based forecasts [1]. This is particularly important in areas such as energy systems, climate modeling, and environmental planning, where decisions must often be made under uncertainty and carry significant economic or operational consequences. Our software addresses this need by providing a streamlined and effective framework for converting ensemble forecasts — such as those generated by weather simulations from ECMWF [2] — into accurate probabilistic forecasts.

Minimizing uncertainty is a universal goal in all forecasting domains, and our software package Neural Adaptive Basis for (time-adaptive) Quantile Regression, NABQR, provides a novel way to achieve it. Assume some (pre-existing) ensembles exist. That is, scenarios describing possible future developments. We wish to convert them into accurate quantile-based predictions. This process is broadly relevant, as such predictions can be applied to many areas, including risk management in finance, electricity markets, and production. We have applied NABQR to wind forecasting with strong results, demonstrating how refined ensemble forecasts translate into more reliable quantile estimates and improve forecast accuracy [3].

Neural networks systematically correct ensemble forecasts, followed by time-adaptive quantile regression (TAQR) to estimate conditional quantile forecasts. This approach reduces quantile crossings and enhances forecast reliability. It supports scientific discovery by allowing

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Table 1
List of abbreviations.

Abbreviation	Description
CRPS	Continuous Ranked Probability Score
MAE	Mean Absolute Error
QSS	Quantile Skill Score
TAQR	Time-Adaptive Quantile Regression
NABQR	Neural Adaptive Basis Quantile Regression
CSV	Comma-Separated Values

users to incorporate data-driven corrections into their pipelines. Recent research on improving wind power prediction densities [3] shows how TAQR applied to refined ensembles leads to superior forecast distributions.

Using the software is straightforward: users supply ensemble forecasts and specify their target quantiles. The neural network component — drawing inspiration from architectures such as N-BEATS [4] — discovers basis functions that capture evolving data patterns, and an efficient TAQR solver [5] then produces calibrated quantiles. The open-source package, hosted on GitHub,¹ ensures transparency, reproducibility, and opportunities for community-driven enhancements. Its ease of integration facilitates adoption into broader workflows, enabling model comparison, scenario testing, and iterative improvements.

Our approach builds on and extends a rich body of literature. Quantile regression has a long history in statistical modeling [6], while neural networks have enabled flexible functional approximations [4,7,8]. Ensemble-based methods from state-of-the-art weather forecasting centers [2] naturally inform our inputs for probabilistic modeling. By combining ensemble calibration, neural network corrections, and time-adaptive quantile regression, our software creates a cohesive, methodologically sound, and practically useful framework. Its combination of neural network-based calibration, TAQR modeling, and user-friendly interfaces serves as a catalyst for advancing the state of the art in probabilistic forecasting and fostering scientific insights across diverse fields.

2. Software description

NABQR is an open-source Python package designed to enhance the accuracy and reliability of probabilistic forecasts. Built for flexibility and ease of integration, NABQR corrects ensemble forecasts using Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM) networks and applies Time-Adaptive Quantile Regression (TAQR) to produce optimal predictive distributions.

The software is implemented entirely in Python (compatible with version 3.10 and above). It adheres to modern software development practices, including modular design, comprehensive documentation, and integration with widely-used libraries such as TensorFlow, NumPy, and pandas. NABQR supports various input formats and produces results in accessible formats like CSV and NumPy arrays, facilitating seamless incorporation into existing workflows.

NABQR provides users with a streamlined pipeline for processing ensemble data, training neural networks, and applying quantile regression methods.

For comprehensive and well-documented examples, users are encouraged to visit the following ReadTheDocs.² The documentation describes its usage in full detail.

NABQR has been tailored specifically to work well with wind power production forecasting in Denmark. Running the software with almost no tuning provides upwards of 40% improvements in the mean absolute sense for specific areas [3].

2.1. Software architecture

NABQR's Application Programming Interface (API) is designed to be compatible with the widely-used TensorFlow library [9], facilitating seamless integration into existing machine learning workflows. The package supports established data formats, such as NumPy arrays [10] and pandas data frames [11], ensuring ease of use and interoperability. Data generated by NABQR can be saved in pickle, NumPy, or CSV formats, allowing for flexible data handling and inspection.

To enhance extensibility and maintainability, NABQR employs object-oriented design principles, particularly when dealing with neural networks. This approach modularizes the framework, with each component encapsulated within a class or function. The repositories adhere to the Black³ coding style to ensure consistency and enhance readability.

Additionally, NABQR includes a comprehensive Python module that implements TAQR, featuring user-friendly function wrappers. The framework's components are integrated into a central `Pipeline` function wrapper, providing users with access to a variety of convenient methods, including logging and visualization capabilities, see Fig. 1. NABQR can be easily incorporated into Python scripts or Jupyter Notebooks, supporting tasks such as training LSTM networks, executing TAQR algorithms, or running the entire pipeline. NABQR primarily consists of 5 Python modules:

- **functions_for_TAQR.py:** This module contains the main functions of TAQR. It includes algorithms for updating and solving quantile regression problems using the simplex method.
- **functions.py:** This module provides core functionalities for the NABQR framework, including scoring metrics such as Variogram, CRPS, MAE and QSS. It also includes functions for dataset creation, preprocessing, and model definitions, as well as the implementation of the TAQR algorithm.
- **helper_functions.py:** This module offers utility functions that support the main operations of the NABQR framework. It includes functions for data manipulation, and simulating correlated AR(1) processes as well as more advanced and realistic wind power production (see `simulate_wind_power_sde`), which is used for generating synthetic datasets and testing robustness.
- **nabqr.py:** This is the main interface for running the NABQR pipeline. It integrates ensemble generation, model training, and visualization capabilities, providing a comprehensive pipeline for executing the NABQR methodology from data simulation to result visualization. This is also where simulated data can be generated.
- **visualization.py:** This module is responsible for visualizing the results of the NABQR models. It includes functions to generate plots that illustrate the performance of the quantile regression models, helping users interpret and analyze the probabilistic forecasts effectively and ensure consistency in plotting, for example using functionalities from `matplotlib.mdates.AutoDateLocator` and a dynamic way to plot the number of ensembles.

The code is well-documented and easy to navigate, and people are welcome to make changes to their copy of the package under the MIT license.

2.2. Software functionalities

NABQR trains an LSTM network to correct the ensembles, to be more reliable, and to have a better quantile score. We optimize for a multidimensional quantile loss function; that is, we optimize for all quantiles in the same network, and not a separate network for each quantile. The output of the LSTM network is used as a basis matrix for a time-adaptive quantile regression algorithm, which produces probabilistic multivariate forecasts. Probabilistic forecast measures have

¹ <https://github.com/bast0320/nabqr>

² <https://nabqr.readthedocs.io/en/latest>

³ <https://github.com/psf/black>

been implemented to readily calculate a range of scores: MAE, CRPS, Variogram-Score, Quantile Score, and reliability plots.

To install the package run:

```
>> pip install nabqr
```

2.2.1. Submodules

NABQR provides practical and useful wrapper functions. We will use the notation `function() → (output1, \ldots)` to explain the following functions. For more information, see the documentation.

```
calculate_scores() → (MAE, QS, CRPS, VarS)
```

When provided with the observations, TAQR predictions, and ensembles, this function will output MAE, QS, CRPS, and VarS scores to evaluate the probabilistic forecast's performance.

```
simulate_wind_power_sde() → (ensembles, y)
```

Simulates normalized wind power production using an Ornstein–Uhlenbeck process with GARCH volatility and jumps of normally distributed sizes driven by a Poisson process. The mean reversion is state-dependent with a repelling mechanism near 1.0 (upper boundary), and the diffusion term vanishes at the boundaries to avoid unphysical values outside $[0, 1]$. Returns ensembles and observations (y).

```
run_taqr(x, y, q_list, n_init, n_full) → (q_hat, y, beta)
```

Executes the full TAQR algorithm from timestep $t_{n_{\text{init}}}$ to $t_{n_{\text{full}}}$ [5]. It employs `one_step_quantile_prediction()`, which can run the TAQR algorithm for at least one timestep and up to all available timesteps for a single quantile. Returns the predicted quantiles \hat{q} , observations, y , for convenience, and the time-adaptive parameters, β .

```
run_nabqr_pipeline(x, y, ...) → (scores,
                               corrected_ensembles, q_hat, ...)
```

Fig. 1 shows the step in the pipeline function. The workflow involves loading and preparing ensemble data and observations, followed by training an LSTM network on approximately 70% of the data to update the basis matrix. Once the data is corrected, the TAQR algorithm is initialized on a small subset and applied to the test set. The results are then prepared by cleaning missing values (NaNs) and evaluating MAE, CRPS, VarS, QS, and reliability. Finally, probabilistic forecasts are visualized for interpretation and analysis. Returns the calculated scores, corrected ensembles, \hat{q} . For the full output and the files it saves, please see the documentation.

2.3. Time consumption

The software runs on a 2020 MacBook Pro M1. We simulate 10,000 data points including 33 ensembles in 0.33 s. This produces 2998 TAQR predictions, corresponding to the last 30% of the dataset.

Initially, we need to train the LSTM network and solve a small quantile regression problem to obtain the parameters for each quantile. The actual runtime of fitting the initial guess for the TAQR algorithm is negligible compared to training the LSTM network for 200 epochs. The initial TAQR fitting only uses 200 data points and runs in less than a second for all quantiles. The initial training of the LSTM network takes 1056.35 s (5.28s/epoch) and, therefore, cannot be run online, e.g., for 15 min data.

Computing 10 equidistant quantiles within the 5%–95% range takes 74.08 s. Appendix B provides a detailed breakdown of the computation time for each quantile, showing that it takes more time to estimate central quantiles due to the higher density of data in these regions.

Table 2

Performance metrics for different ensemble correction methods.

Metric	MAE	CRPS	Variogram	QS
Ensembles	0.0878	0.0657	0.0009	0.0505
LSTM Ensembles	0.0880	0.0667	0.00096	0.0310
NABQR	0.0825	0.0579	0.00102	0.0286

2.4. Limitations

Thus far, NABQR has been examined solely with scenario-based inputs. A critical requirement is that these inputs must span the full range of the data; otherwise, the network cannot be properly trained under its current configuration. Addressing this limitation would require reformulating the current LSTM network as a Quantile Regression Neural Network (QRNN).

Another limitation of the method is the time and computational cost of (re)training the LSTM network, which is too high for an online implementation. Simple modifications, such as including less history or fewer epochs, would make it feasible to run it online.

3. Illustrative examples

Running the `run_nabqr_pipeline` with the only inputs being wind power production data, (X =ensembles, y =observations), will create Fig. 2 as in [3].

Initially, the code imports essential components, including NABQR helper functions, the SciencePlots plotting library, and the datetime library. Subsequently, a synthetic dataset is generated for testing purposes. An example of using the `simulate_wind_power_sde`, can be seen in Appendix A. The final section of the code executes the entire pipeline, specifying the dataset, the training size for the LSTM network, the time steps (representing the lagged values for the LSTM network), and the quantiles for the TAQR algorithm. Running the pipeline with absolute minimum input specification leads to an improvement of the simulated data of 45% in Quantile Score (QS), 11% in Mean Absolute Error (MAE), and 14% in Continuous Ranked Probability Score (CRPS). Table 2 shows the actual scores. An explanation of the error metrics can be found in [3]. Fig. 2 shows predictions for real-life wind power production [3].

4. Impact

The NABQR package improves renewable energy power production forecasts, achieving up to 40% better accuracy in terms of mean absolute error compared to previous state-of-the-art commercial forecasts. This directly impacts the efficiency and sustainability of power grid operations. By improving forecast accuracy, NABQR reduces reliance on backup power plants, thereby decreasing CO2 emissions and supporting the green transition. This advancement encourages investment and innovation in renewable energy and accelerates the transition to sustainable energy sources.

NABQR democratizes advanced machine learning techniques, making them accessible to a wider audience beyond domain experts. This aligns with the principles of human-centered AI, promoting transparency, collaboration, and inclusivity. By simplifying machine learning pipelines, NABQR reduces the need for manual trial-and-error, streamlining the knowledge discovery process and empowering users to efficiently manage and analyze datasets.

Written in Python and thoroughly documented, NABQR is set to be used in both academic and industrial settings. This accessibility invites further exploration of neural networks as optimal basis function generators, fostering new research opportunities and advancements in the field.

Fig. 1. Overview of pipeline in NABQR. Note that for the first step if data is not specified to be loaded the pipeline will automatically simulate data.

Fig. 2. Excerpt of TAQR predictions with prediction interval 5%–95% shown in shades of blue for Denmark (area DK2) Offshore wind power production. Obtained by running `run_nabqr_pipeline` on wind power production.

5. Conclusion

NABQR is an open-source Python package designed to correct scenarios and produce more accurate reliable probabilistic forecasts. NABQR uses neural networks and time-adaptive quantile regression. The NABQR package includes the first time-adaptive quantile regression algorithm written in Python along with useful wrapper functions for e.g. visualizing probabilistic forecasts, training LSTM networks, and simulating realistic wind power.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Bastian Schmidt Jørgensen: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Validation, Software, Project administration, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Jan Kloppenborg Møller:** Writing – review & editing, Validation, Supervision, Software, Methodology. **Peter Nystrup:** Writing – review & editing, Validation, Supervision, Methodology, Data

curation. **Henrik Madsen:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Resources, Project administration, Methodology, Investigation, Funding acquisition, Formal analysis, Conceptualization.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Acknowledgments

This work is supported by *IIRES* (Energy Cluster Denmark), *SEM4Cities* (Innovation Fund Denmark, No. 0143-0004), *ELEXIA* (Horizon Europe No. 101075656), and the projects *DynFlex* and *PtXMarkets*, which both are part of the Danish Mission Green Fuel portfolio of projects.

Personal acknowledgments

Thanks to Peder Bacher and Goran Goranovic for good discussions.

Appendix A. Example of simulated data

Fig. A.3 shows a simulation for 250 h ahead for normalized wind power data with initial conditions

$$\begin{aligned}
 X_0 &= 0.6, \\
 \theta &= 0.77, \\
 \kappa &= 0.12, \\
 \sigma_{\text{base}} &= 1.05, \\
 \alpha &= 0.57, \\
 \beta &= 1.2, \\
 \lambda_{\text{jump}} &= 0.045, \\
 \mu_{\text{jump}} &= 0.0, \\
 \sigma_{\text{jump}} &= 0.1.
 \end{aligned}$$

Fig. A.3. Simulation for 250 h of normalized wind power data including ensembles with the method `simulate_wind_power_sde` in `run_nabqr_pipeline`.

Table B.3

TAQR computation times for different quantiles.

Quantile	Time (s)
0.05	4.869
0.15	4.649
0.25	6.316
0.35	7.225
0.45	7.416
0.55	7.046
0.65	6.662
0.75	6.397
0.85	4.851
0.95	3.516

For an interpretation and explanation of the initial conditions, we refer to the documentation.⁴

Appendix B. Specification of time consumption per quantile

See Table B.3.

Data availability

The authors do not have permission to share data, but simulated data is available in NABQR.

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⁴ https://nabqr.readthedocs.io/en/latest/api.html#nabqr.helper_functions.simulate_wind_power_sde